

Review on covid-19 vaccination

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For the first time in the human history, the world has derived with safe and efficacious vaccine within a time period of approximately 14 to 16 months, as it is being known that for a vaccine to be developed it requires around 10 to 15 years, which is almost one-tenth of the traditional time. So as to stop the spread of a viral disease, proper medication should need to be developed which will either stop the spreading or reduce the chance of getting infected and vaccine is the only medication which can be used as an outcome of the disease. SARS-CoV (Severe Acute respiratory Syndrome Corona virus -2) also known as coronavirus is a RNA virus with zoonotic origin, first emerged in year 2002 and then in year 2019(Covid-19), named as corona because of the presence of a crown like protein at the surface of virus. SARS-CoV-2 declared pandemic in March 2021 by WHO (World Health Organization) as it was spreading rapidly among human. To stop its further spread, it becomes compulsory to develop a vaccine against the virus. Scientists from different research laboratories worldwide have used several mechanisms for vaccine development, most of them focus on neutralizing the spike protein by developing antibodies against it. All accessible vaccines of covid-19 are grouped under four categories whole virus vaccines, viral vector vaccines, nucleic acid vaccines, and recombinant protein-based vaccine. Currently, there are 18 emergency approved vaccines in the world for vaccination among large population to develop herd immunity in which all the vaccines used different technique, each vaccines having their advantages and disadvantages. Therefore, this review paper will focus on all the different techniques along with their advantages and side effects by conducting a survey among 500 people in a state.

Keywords: Covid-19, Corona Virus, Vaccination